

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.3

Risultati di analisi di casi studio di elementi strutturali e di interi edifici

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 1.3

Rezultati analiz konstrukcijskih elementov in stavb

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.3 Results of case studies analysis of structural elements and entire buildings

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Report 1.3

Results of case studies analysis of structural elements and entire buildings

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.3 of the PRO-SIS project, titled “Case study analysis of structural elements and entire buildings to be used for the calibration of analytical models and intermediate-level numerical models”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

In the previous report “REPORT 1.1: Analytic model for dimensioning” [1] the “CONSTRAIN” experimental results were gathered and critically reviewed and a first calibration of analytical-mechanical models capable to describe the experimental behaviour was presented.

Then, in “REPORT 1.2: Numerical models for simulating the behaviour of reinforced elements/buildings” [2], advanced numerical models were developed by using two different finite element software (ABAQUS and OOFEM) and were used to simulate the behaviour of the CONSTRAIN experimental samples (masonry piers and spandrels) strengthened with Composite Reinforced Mortar (CRM). The ABAQUS models were developed by the University of Ljubljana (UL FGG), while the OOFEM models by the University of Trieste (DIA – UNITS).

In this REPORT 1.3, the advanced numerical models, previously developed and validated, are used for the simulation of case studies of increasing complexity, ranging from single structural elements to entire buildings. Both unreinforced and CRM strengthened masonry configurations are analysed and compared. The results of the analyses provide a valuable reference for designers and researchers and allow for the calibration of more simplified numerical models in the next project steps.

Coherently with the approach applied in [2], once the characteristics of the various configurations to be analyzed were agreed upon, the two partners autonomously carried out the simulations and compared the results at the end.

The report starts describing the main characteristics of the defined case studies. Then, there are the two main sections of the report, one for each type modelling developed. For each section, the first part briefly summarizes the modelling approach, then the numeric results are presented and analyzed. At the end, a final section provides the overall final remarks on the obtained results.

2. Benchmark examples

The main geometrical and mechanical characteristics of the analysed configurations are described in the following. The modelling assumptions are listed, and the naming conventions adopted for the examples is explained.

2.1. Pier elements

The benchmark pier element is made of single leaf solid brick masonry (type B1, as calibrated in [2]), with main dimensions $1250 \times 1250 \times 250 \text{ mm}^3$ (width x height x thickness). It is subjected to a constant axial stress of 0.5 MPa applied at the top (the masonry self-weight is neglected in all models). The rotation is constrained at both the base and the top and the horizontal displacement is gradually increased at the top (i.e., shear-type scheme).

Starting from this benchmark, different variations are considered and analysed:

- material: type R2, as calibrated in [2] (rubble stone masonry, 350 mm thick);
- geometry: width 850 mm, 2250 mm and 3350 mm.
- axial stress: 0.3 MPa;
- boundary conditions: the rotation is released at the top (i.e. cantilever scheme).

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structural element (P for “pier”), the masonry (B1 for single leaf brick masonry or R2 for double leaf rubble stone masonry), the configuration (U, R1 and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively). Then, there is the varying geometry parameter (the width: 1250, 2250, 3350 or 850 mm), the axial stress level (05 or 03, for 0.5 or 0.3 MPa) and the static scheme (either shear-type or cantilever).

2.2. Spandrel elements

The benchmark spandrel element is made of single leaf masonry (type B1), with main dimensions $1200 \times 1200 \times 250 \text{ mm}^3$ (width x height x thickness) and having in addition a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. The reference configuration consists in reproducing a shear-type scheme for the spandrel (i.e. left pier fixed at the base, right pier moving vertically, with rotations avoided at the base). Unstrengthened (U) and CRM strengthened configurations at one and both sides (R1 and R2) are analysed and compared.

Starting from this benchmark, different variations are considered:

- geometry: spandrel height 1500 mm and 800 mm;
- material: type R2, as calibrated in [2] (rubble stone masonry, 350 mm thick);
- lintel: presence of a 150 mm thick wooden lintel inserted for 150 mm at both ends;
- presence of a horizontal steel tie at the mid height of the spandrel (tensile resistance 100 kN);

- boundary conditions/loading scheme: cantilever beam scheme (i.e. release of the in-plane rotation at the base of the right pier);
- boundary conditions/loading scheme: identical rotations at the base of the piers are applied.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structural element (S for “spandrel”), the masonry (B1 or R2), the configuration (U, R1 and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively). Then, there is the varying geometry parameter (the height: 1000, 1500 and 800 mm). Label “ltl” refers to wooden lintel; the absence/presence of the horizontal tie is indicated with label “t0” or “t1”, respectively. Label “ct” indicates the released rotation at the right pier, label “rot” identical rotations applied at the base. The capacity curves of the benchmark spandrel are reported in dashed lines in the other graphs, for comparison.

2.3. Single-storey walls

The benchmark single-storey wall is made of single leaf masonry (type B1), with main dimensions 5600x3850x250 mm³ (width x height x thickness). It has two symmetric windows 1200x1400 mm² at a distance of 1150 mm from lateral ends and 1000 mm from the floor (Fig. 2.1). The spandrels have a gross height of 1450 mm, including also a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. A horizontal steel tie at the mid height of the spandrel (tensile resistance 100 kN) is introduced.

Fig. 2.1 Main geometric features of the single storey wall.

The masonry self-weight is considered; in addition, the wall is subjected to a constant vertical load at the top. The different levels of axial stress are analysed, considering different values of constant vertical load at the top:

- 14.3 kN/m (additional compressive stress on the piers ~0.1 MPa);
- 42.9 kN/m (additional compressive stress on the piers ~0.3 MPa);
- 71.5 kN/m (additional compressive stress on the piers ~0.5 MPa).

Unstrengthened (U) and CRM strengthened configurations at one and both sides (R1 and R2) are analysed and compared.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structure (SW for “Single storey Wall”), the masonry type (B1), the presence of the horizontal tie (t1), the configuration (U, R1

and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively) and the axial stress level (01, 03 and 05).

2.4. Two-story walls

Two benchmark examples are considered for the two-story walls configurations. They are both made of single leaf masonry (type B1) and have main dimensions $5750 \times 6000 \times 250$ mm³ (width x height x thickness). One (configuration "a" - Fig. 2.2a) is symmetric and has two aligned identical windows at each story (dimensions 1200×1400 mm²). The other (configuration "b" -- Fig. 2.2b) has a window and a door (1200×2100 mm²) at the ground floor, and a single window at the first floor (aligned with that at the ground floor). All the openings include a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. A horizontal steel tie at the mid height of the spandrels (tensile resistance 100 kN) is also introduced.

Fig. 2.2 Main geometric features of the two-storey walls: (a) TWA and (b) TWb.

The masonry self-weight is considered; in addition, the wall is subjected to a constant vertical load at the top, so that the additional compressive stress on the piers of the first floor corresponds approximately to 0.3 MPa. In particular, the additional vertical load applied is 42.9 kN/m for the configuration "a", and 59.4 kN/m for the configuration "b".

Unstrengthened (U) and CRM strengthened configurations at one and both sides (R1 and R2) are analysed and compared.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structure and configuration (TWA or TWb(+)/ TWb(-), for "Two-storey Wall" with configuration "a" or "b", with "b" loaded in both positive and negative direction), the masonry type (B1), the presence of the horizontal tie (t1), the configuration (U, R1 and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively) and the mean axial at the first floor (03).

2.5. Pilot building

The benchmark building herein considered is a two storey building made of single leaf masonry (type B1), with main plan dimensions 5750x4350 mm² and a height of 6000 mm. It features four bearing walls (Fig. 2.3), an intermediate floor of 70 kN and a gabled timber roof of 50 kN (main direction E-W). All the openings include a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. Horizontal steel ties (tensile resistance 100 kN), oriented in both the N-S and E-W directions are located just below the intermediate floor and roof level.

Unstrengthened (U) masonry and masonry strengthened with CRM applied at the outer surface (R1) are analysed and compared.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structure (GB is for "Global building"), the masonry type (B1) and the configuration (U and R1).

Fig. 2.3 Main geometric features of the building.

3. Modelling with ABAQUS (by UL-FGG)

3.1. Main features

The numerical models represent the actual geometry and boundary conditions of the samples. An example of a pier and a spandrel is shown in Fig. 3.1. In the model, there are separate meshes for finite elements representing masonry, mortar coating and glass fibre mesh, and each material has its own nonlinear material model.

Fig. 3.1 Finite element mesh for piers (a) and for spandrels (b) with boundary conditions and loads.

Both the masonry and the mortar coating were modelled as a continuum using 3D solid linear brick elements (C3D8R) with eight nodes and reduced integration, ensuring computational efficiency and stability in explicit dynamic simulations. The glass fibre mesh, on the other hand, was represented using T3D2 elements, 2-node linear 3D truss elements, which was incorporated into the models as a separate component with lengths and positions taken from the tested pier and spandrels.

The material model for masonry and mortar was the well-known Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, which is reliable and proven for analysis of brittle materials such as masonry and concrete. The material parameters were painstakingly determined from tests on materials (compression tests) and by calibration with tests results of piers and spandrels (see PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2]). The material model for GFRP was a perfectly brittle elastic model. The rupture stress was obtained from the measured rupture force of each type of fibre (weft or warped).

Explicit dynamic analyses were used for simulations. The advantages of such analysis for modelling brittle response are well known (stability, less convergence issues). The minimum and maximum time increment in the analyses were 0.000001 s and 0.001 s, respectively, depending on the type of simulation. The size of the time increments was determined by a dedicated parametric analysis to find the optimal balance between accuracy and computation time. To speed up the analyses, mass scaling was used. Mass was scaled by a factor that

produced the target time increment of 0.001 s for pilot building analyses and 0.0001-0.00008 s for other simulations, and dedicated analyses confirmed that the effect of mass scaling on accuracy was negligible.

A detailed description of the numerical models can be found in PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2].

3.2. Parametric analysis on pier elements

The response of walls is herein represented by a pushover force-displacement response curve, and a plot of the logarithmic elastic strains. The concentrations of strains indicate locations of expected damage. The scale on all strain plots in Section 3 of this report is the same and is shown in Fig. 3.2.

Fig. 3.2 The scale of strain plots in the entire report.

The effects first analysed on 1250 mm long piers (Fig. 3.3). As the results show, adding layers of coating increases strength, displacement capacity and ductility of piers. Furthermore, the failure mechanism also changes. In the case of unstrengthened pier, the failure is in shear. Pier strengthened on one side exhibits shear failure, but with clear elements of bending response in the form of horizontal damage at the corners. Finally, the pier strengthened on both sides responds strongly in bending.

In the second stage, the effect of strengthening is analysed on slender piers with a length of 850 mm (Fig. 3.4) and squat piers with a length of 2250 mm (Fig. 3.5) and 3350 mm (Fig. 3.6). As before, the effect of strengthening on pushover force-displacement response curves is clear. Increasing the amount of coating increases strength, displacement capacity and ductility of piers. For slender walls the response mechanism changes from shear to bending due to coating, whereas for squat walls with length of 2250 mm and more, the response mechanism remains shear regardless of amount of coating.

The effect of increasing the length of the piers is that piers get substantially stronger. The effect on ductility and displacement capacity, on the other hand, is relatively small.

Fig. 3.3 The effect of strengthening on 1250 mm long piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right.

Fig. 3.4 The effect of strengthening on 850 mm long piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to 1250 mm long walls.

Fig. 3.5 The effect of strengthening on 2250 mm long piers. Pushover curves force-displacement are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to 1250 mm long walls.

Fig. 3.6 The effect of strengthening on 3350 mm long piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to 1250 mm long walls.

The effect of vertical stress on the wall is analysed next by changing the vertical stress from the original 0.5 to 0.3 MPa. The responses of both walls are compared in Fig. 3.7, where grey curves denote response of highly stressed piers, and coloured curves denote response of lightly stressed piers. Reducing the vertical stress clearly reduces strength of the walls in case of both, unstrengthened and strengthened configurations, but the effect on the displacement capacity and ductility appears to be relatively small. Although the curves do not change much due to the reduced vertical load, the response mechanism becomes much more bending like, with a lot of strain concentrations in the corners (bottom left and top right corner in Fig. 3.7).

Fig. 3.7 Response of wall with smaller vertical stress. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to the wall with 0.5 MPa vertical stress.

Fig. 3.8 shows the response of 1250 mm long walls if top rotation is freed (cantilever type of boundary conditions). Unstrengthened pier and pier strengthened on only one side fail in pure bending, and the resistance of such walls under cantilever boundary conditions is drastically lower.

Fig. 3.8 Response of brick piers under cantilever boundary conditions. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey curves correspond to the wall with clamped boundary conditions.

The response of unstrengthened *stone* masonry under reduced vertical stress and under cantilever boundary conditions is shown Fig. 3.9. Simulations indicate that the principal effect of reduced vertical stress is the reduction of shear resistance. Changing the boundary conditions, on the other hand, drastically changes the response. The cantilever wall exhibits a large reduction of stiffness and strength compared to the clamped one. Additionally, the failure mechanism changes from shear to bending.

Fig. 3.9 Response of stone piers with smaller vertical stress and cantilever boundary conditions. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and damage on the right.

The effect of geometry on seismic response of stone masonry piers is analysed in Fig. 3.10. Increasing the length of the walls increases strength of the walls and displacement at peak strength. The response mechanism in all cases is shear.

Fig. 3.10 Effect of geometry on the response on unstrengthened stone masonry piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown at the top and strain concentrations at the bottom. The grey curves correspond to the (thinner) single wythe brick walls.

3.3. Parametric analysis on spandrel elements

The results shown in Fig. 3.11 compare the response of unstrengthened 1200 mm tall spandrel with that of spandrels with coating on one and both sides. The strength, displacement capacity and ductility strongly increase with coating. The type of damage also changes. The unstrengthened spandrel exhibits only bending damage, evident from two vertical cracks, whereas in the strengthened spandrels, there is diagonal damage, which indicates also shear response. The shear damage is smeared over a large surface, indicating a large area for potential energy dissipation, which is a desired property.

Fig. 3.11 Effect of coating on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right.

The effect of coating on spandrels with different geometries shows the same trend, as can be observed on Fig. 3.12 and Fig. 3.13. Increasing the height of the spandrel also increasing the strength of the spandrel.

The short spandrel with 800 mm height, shown in Fig. 3.12 exhibits lower properties than the benchmark 1200 mm tall spandrel. Furthermore, the response mechanism is much more heavily inclined towards bending, and the damage is much more concentrated in the vertical cracks. This reduces energy dissipation capacity, which is evident from the much more brittle response (faster strength degradation) in the force-displacement response in the graph in Fig. 3.12.

The tallest spandrel, with a height of 1500 mm is the strongest as expected. However, the response mechanism is very similar to the response of the benchmark spandrel. Therefore the response curves (Fig. 3.13), are qualitatively very similar with similar displacement capacity and energy dissipation characteristics.

Fig. 3.12 The response of 800 mm tall spandrels with different amount of strengthening. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of 1200 mm tall spandrels.

Fig. 3.13 Effect of coating on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of 1200 mm tall spandrels.

The effect of steel rod at the middle of the spandrel (Fig. 3.14), which is often installed during seismic strengthening, is analysed next. The effect is shown for 1200 mm, 800 mm and 1500 mm tall spandrels in Fig. 3.15, Fig. 3.16 and Fig. 3.17, respectively. The effect of the steel rod is that the response in terms of strength, displacement capacity, energy dissipation capacity and ductility increases. The increase is the biggest for 800 mm tall piers. The high strains appear to be smeared across a larger area in case steel rod is used, because the effect of the rod is similar to the effect of the compressive force in piers – compression generally improves the response, unless there is too much of it. In that case, the walls become brittle. However, in spandrels the effects of compression are only positive because axial stress in masonry is still quite low. The effect of more distributed strains is also positive, because it indicates damage over a larger surface area, which results in increased capacity of the wall to dissipate energy.

Fig. 3.14 Location of steel rod (red line).

Fig. 3.15 Effect of steel rod on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of a spandrel without the rod.

Fig. 3.16 Effect of steel rod on the response on 800 mm tall brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of a spandrel without the rod.

Fig. 3.17 Effect of steel rod on the response on 1500 mm tall brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of a spandrel without the rod.

The last analysis shows the effect of vertical compression in piers on the response of spandrels. The results are shown in Fig. 3.18. Reducing the stress from 0.5 MPa to 0.3 MPa only has a negligible effect on the response. It should be noted that the present continuum model is not the most suitable for such analysis, because the main effect of compression in piers is to increase friction in vertical bending cracks. In any case, the effect of the vertical stress in the piers is expected to be low, just perhaps not as low as the results in Fig. 3.18 indicate.

Fig. 3.18 Effect of compressive stress in piers on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curve is shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right.

3.4. Parametric analysis on single-story walls

The geometry and boundary conditions of the numerical model to simulate single-story walls are shown in Fig. 4.10. All solid elements are of “masonry” type. Bottom plane is completely restrained (displacements u_x , u_y , u_z). Masonry jack arches are connected to masonry via friction contact with friction coefficient of 0.5.

The analysis is divided into two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top is gradually increased. The horizontal displacement is imposed over the whole top plane.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.11, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 3.19 Numerical model for parametric analyses on single storey wall.

The results show clear correlation between vertical load and failure mechanism. Walls under low vertical load experience bending failure whereas walls under high vertical load tend to fail in shear failure. With increasing amount of strengthening the response becomes more inclined towards bending.

Fig. 3.20 Numerical parametric analyses on a single storey wall: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of axial stress level.

3.5. Parametric analysis of two-story walls

The main features of the numerical model to simulate two-story walls are summarized in Fig. 4.10. All solid elements are of “masonry” type. All displacement in the bottom plane are restrained (u_x , u_y , u_z). Masonry jack arches are connected to masonry via friction contact with friction coefficient of 0.5.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top and at the intermediate floor (at a height of 3 m) is gradually increased. It is imposed via rigid body that rotates in accordance to wall's stiffness. Displacement is controlled in the middle of the rigid body.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.11, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 3.21 Numerical model for parametric analyses on two-storey wall.

In both configurations of unstrengthened samples, the response of two storey walls can be described as a combination of shear and bending mechanisms in both piers and spandrels. With higher amount of strengthening, the damage localizes more at the 1st floor and becomes more inclined towards bending failure. The direction of displacement in unsymmetric walls has an effect on damage formation (shear/bending) but not on maximum resistance.

Fig. 3.22 Numerical parametric analyses on the two storey walls: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the different wall configurations.

3.6. Parametric analysis on buildings

The benchmark building considered in this section is a two-storey building made of double leaf stone masonry (type R2), strengthened on one side (Fig. 3.23). Because the building was tested within the CONSTRAIN project, the actual response is known. The purpose of the parametric analysis is to investigate the effect of strengthening on both sides and the effect of strengthening on a building that is made of bricks (B1). These two scenarios were not tested within the CONSTRAIN project.

In the brick model, there are 250 mm high masonry jack arches above doors and windows. In the stone masonry building, the lintels are wooden.

Fig. 3.23 View of the ABAQUS model of the pilot building with loads and boundary conditions.

In the first step, the response of the numerical model is compared to the experiment. The comparison is shown in Fig. 3.24. The response of the structure during the experiment is shown by two green curves, which indicate displacements at the left and right of the structure at first floor. The numerical results are shown by a black line, which is averaged for both sides. The alignment between the experimental tests and numerical results serve as further validation of the numerical model.

Fig. 3.24 Comparison of pushover force-displacement curves of experiment and numerical model: unstrengthened sample U (a) and strengthened on one side R1 (b).

In the first parametric analysis, the stone masonry pilot building is numerically analysed for cases when it is unstrengthened (U) and when it is strengthened the outer surface (R1) and both surfaces (R2). The case when the coating is not anchored into the foundation is considered first. The results are shown in (Fig. 3.25). It should be noted that such application is not correct, and its purpose is to show how much worse it is compared to the correct application. Despite the lack of anchoring, the strengthening substantially improves the response, as one-sided coating substantially increases strength, displacement capacity and ductility. Two-sided coating increases these characteristics even further.

Fig. 3.25 Effect of strengthening on the response of stone masonry pilot building. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right.

In the previous model, the building was not anchored into the ground. If CONSTRAINT strengthening is applied properly, the fibres are anchored into the foundations and prevent uplift. Such a case is shown in Fig. 3.26, and exhibits a much-improved response. In case of single-sided strengthening, the resistance increases by about 20 % (from about 500 kN to about 600 kN). In case of two-sided strengthening, the effect is even larger. The increase in strength

is about 30 % (from about 650 kN to about 850 kN). The conclusion is that it is vital to anchor the coating into the foundation and provide continuity of the GFRP mesh everywhere.

Fig. 3.26 Effect of strengthening on the response of stone masonry pilot building. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey lines show the response of a model not anchored into the ground.

Finally, the material of the pilot building is changed to single leaf brick type (B1) of masonry (the thickness of the walls remains the same). Such a structure has better material properties and better seismic response with much higher strength and similar displacement capacity and ductility, as can be seen in Fig. 3.27.

Fig. 3.27 Effect of strengthening on the response of brick masonry pilot building. Pushover curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey lines show the response of a stone masonry building.

4. Modelling with OOFEM (by DIA – UNITS)

4.1. Main features

The main features of the advanced numerical model developed by using OOFEM are herein briefly described. Detailed description of the model and material characteristics can be found in PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2].

The OOFEM models are based on 20-node brick elements with dimensions of $167 \times 167 \times T$ mm³, where T represents the overall wall thickness. The elements feature layered cross sections, with layers arranged through the thickness, so to represent the original masonry, the fiber-based reinforcement, and the mortar coating. Nonlinear static analyses, accounting for material nonlinearities, are performed under displacement control. The materials (Table 4.1) are considered as homogeneous and isotropic (concrete-damage plasticity material model for both the masonry and the mortar coating, to account both cracking and crushing, and an isotropic damage model to the fiber-based reinforcement layer, to account for tensile failure).

Table 4.1 Main numerical parameters adopted for the OOFEM numerical simulations

	B1 masonry	Mortar	
Material type	<i>Cdpm2</i>	<i>Cdpm2</i>	
Secant Young's modulus E	1.64 GPa	14.4 GPa	
Initial Young's modulus E_{init}	4.92 GPa	14.4 GPa	
Poisson modulus n	0.45	0.25	
Self-weight γ	18 kN/m ³	20 kN/m ³	
Comp. strength f_c	3.84 MPa	0.85 MPa	
Tensile strength f_t	0.162 MPa	0.85 MPa	
Softening law	Linear	Bilinear	
Hardening parameters	b_h	0.015	0.002
	h_p	0.0	0.0
	k_{init}	0.15	0.10
Softening parameters	w_f/h	0.004	0.035
	a_{soft}	8.0	4
	f_{t1}	-	0.45
	w_{f1}/h	-	0.0045

	GFRP
Material type	<i>ldm1</i>
Young's modulus E	3.81 GPa
Poisson modulus n	0.01
Comp. strength f_c	0.0
Equiv. strain type	mod.Mises
Peak strain ε_0	1.8%
Damage law	linear
Ultimate strain ε_u	6.0%

4.2. Parametric analysis on pier elements

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on pier elements are summarized in Fig. 4.1. The model consists of a "I"-shaped wall portion, as if it is extracted from the windowed wall of a building, and it is composed of a central pier (1250x1250 mm²) and upper and bottom bands (2000x700 mm²). The perimetral solid elements of the bands are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of "masonry" type.

The solid elements of the lower row are pinned at the base. To reproduce the shear-type scheme, both the vertical load and the increasing horizontal in-plane displacement are applied on the node at the top left corner of the model (Master node). Both the translations and rotations of the Master node, along the out-of-plane direction, are avoided and all other nodes at the top (Slave nodes) are constrained to have the same displacements of the Master node. Differently, to reproduce the cantilever beam scheme, the increasing horizontal displacement is applied on the node at the top left corner, while the vertical load was equally distributed among all the nodes at the top. The translations along the out-of-plane direction are avoided in all the top nodes.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement is gradually increased.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.2 and Fig. 4.3, along with the panel damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode.

The capacity curves represent the trend of the horizontal load varying the net pier displacement (difference between the horizontal displacements at top and bottom of the pier, excluding upper and lower bands.). The capacity curves of the benchmark pier are reported in dashed lines in the other graphs, for comparison

Fig. 4.1 Numerical model for parametric analyses on pier elements.

All the unstrengthened piers with shear-type scheme fail in diagonal shear; the cantilever beam scheme turns the failure in flexural mode.

In the benchmark pier (P-B1-Rx_1250_05_st), the failure of the CRM strengthened samples is still dominated by diagonal shear, although there is also the activation of the flexural mechanism (more pronounced in R2 than R1).

As the axial force decreases (P-B1-Rx_1250_03_st), the resistances reduce and the displacement capacities increase; the collapse mechanism is still dominated by diagonal shear, but the activation of the flexural mechanism becomes more pronounced.

The influence of the masonry type (P-R2-Rx_1250_05_st) is very modest and likely related to the post-elastic characteristics of the material, contrasting more effectively the activation of the flexural mechanism and thus resulting in reduced ultimate displacements.

The free rotation at the top (P-B1-Rx_1250_05_ct) localizes the damage at the base of the pier, which collapses due to bending, at significantly lower force values and higher ultimate displacements; the effectiveness of the reinforcement, in this case, is modest.

Increasing the pier width (P-B1-Rx_2250/3350_05_st), the shear mechanism dominates, while reducing it (P-B1-Rx_850_05_st), also the flexural mechanism activated, until prevailing on shear. It is also observed that the shear damage, which generally localizes along the diagonal of the pier, tends in particularly squat piers to take on an almost tri-linear pattern, with the two extremities more inclined than the panel diagonal and the central branch approximately horizontal.

Fig. 4.2 Numerical parametric analyses on pier elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of axial load, masonry type and boundary conditions.

Fig. 4.3 Numerical parametric analyses on pier elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of pier geometry.

4.3. Parametric analysis on spandrel elements

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on spandrel elements are summarized in Fig. 4.4. The model consists of a "H"-shaped wall portion, as if it is extracted from the windowed wall of a building, and it is composed of a central spandrel (1200x1450 mm²) and two lateral pier portions (1170x3000 mm²) subjected to a constant vertical compressive stress of 0.3 MPa (the masonry self-weight is neglected in all models). The base and top solid elements in the piers are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of "masonry" type. Accordingly to the spandrel model developed in Report 1.2 [2], to represent, in a very simplified way, the extreme weakness of the contact area between the jack arch and the overlaying masonry, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the masonry layer of the mesh elements just above the jack arch.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the vertical uplift at the base of the right pier is applied and gradually increased.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.5-Fig. 4.7, along with the spandrel damage state (principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the shear load acting on the spandrel, varying the spandrel shear distortion (evaluated as the relative vertical displacement measured at the spandrel ends).

Fig. 4.4 Numerical model for parametric analyses on spandrel elements.

All the plain masonry spandrels fail in flexural mode (localized at both ends, or only one in case of "ct" configuration), while the introduction of the horizontal steel tie (S-B1-U_1200_t1) leads to a combined shear-bending collapse.

The CRM strengthened benchmark spandrel (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0) is affected by combined diagonal shear and flexural mechanism.

Decreasing the spandrel height (S-B1-Rx_800_t0), the flexural mechanism dominates, while increasing it (S-B1-Rx_1500_t0) the shear mechanism tends to prevail on bending.

The influence of the masonry type (S-R2-Rx_1200_t0) is quite negligible, since rubble stone masonry R2 is thicker but weaker.

Slightly higher resistances emerge from the configurations with the timber lintel (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0_ltl), even though the shear mechanism is evidently mitigated.

The introduction of the horizontal steel tie (S-B1-Rx_1200_t1), leads to higher resistances and lower displacements capacity, counteracting effectively bending failure towards the diagonal shear collapse.

With the rotational freedom of the right pier (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0_ct), damage localizes mainly at the left end of the spandrel, which collapses due to bending, and the overall structural resistance is significantly reduced.

The base rotation (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0_rot) yields performance equivalent to the benchmark configuration.

Fig. 4.5 Numerical parametric analyses on spandrel elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of spandrel geometry.

Fig. 4.6 Numerical parametric analyses on spandrel elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of masonry type, lintel type and introduction of horizontal tie.

Fig. 4.7 Numerical parametric analyses on spandrel elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the boundary conditions/loading scheme.

4.4. Parametric analysis on single-story walls

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on single-story walls are summarized in Fig. 4.8 Fig. 4.4. The solid elements of the base row are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of “masonry” type. In exception, accordingly to the spandrel model of §4.3, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the mesh elements just above the jack arches.

The solid elements of the base row are pinned at the base. The out of plane displacement at the top were avoided, to represent the constrain provided by an effective connection with the floor.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top is gradually increased.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.9, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 4.8 Numerical model for parametric analyses on single storey wall.

The failure on the unstrengthened wall SW-B1-t1-U_01 is dominated by the bending failure of the three masonry piers; the bending damage affected also the right spandrel. As the axial load increases, also diagonal cracking failure is detected, which tends to prevail over the bending mechanism in the central pier, for SW-B1-t1-U_03, and in both central and right pier, for SW-B1-t1-U_05.

In the R1 configurations, the failure mode is very similar to the respective unstrengthened configuration; however, it is generally observed that the areas where the maximum strains are attained results wider. More extensive damaged areas emerged also in the R2 configurations, in respect to U; in this case, the bending failure of the piers tends to dominate the collapse of the wall also in case of high vertical forces. In general, the increase of the axial force leads to an increase of the resistance; differently, the displacement capacities tend very slightly to increase.

Fig. 4.9 Numerical parametric analyses on a single storey wall: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of axial stress level.

4.5. Parametric analysis of two-story walls

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on two-story walls are summarized in Fig. 4.10. The solid elements of the base row are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of “masonry” type. In exception, accordingly to the spandrel model of §4.3, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the mesh elements just above the jack arches. The first row of solid elements are pinned at the base. The out of plane displacement at the top were avoided, to represent the constrain provided by an effective connection with the top floor.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top and at the intermediate floor (at a height of 3 m) is gradually increased. A constant ratio between the intermediate and top floor displacement was considered (0.5 for TWa and 0.6 for TWb±), so to represent a distribution of lateral forces approximately proportional to the fundamental mode shape.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.11, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 4.10 Numerical model for parametric analyses on two-storey wall.

Even though the dominance of diagonal cracking or bending failure mechanism in single elements varies in the three walls, the performances are quite comparable in terms of global resistance and the damage is mainly localized at the ground floor; also the intermediate spandrels are generally affected by damage, while the damage at the first floor is very limited.

Looking at the R1 configurations, it emerges failure mode very similar to the respective unstrengthened configuration; however, it is the areas with maximum strains are wider (diffusive effect of the reinforcement). Even more extensive maximum strains areas emerged in the R2 configurations. The displacement capacity of all the strengthened walls is remarkable (drifts higher than 1%).

Fig. 4.11 Numerical parametric analyses on the two storey walls: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the different wall configurations.

4.6. Parametric analysis of buildings

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on single storey walls are summarized in Fig. 4.12. The solid elements of the base row are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of “masonry” type. In exception, accordingly to the spandrel model of §4.3, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the mesh elements just above the jack arches. The solid elements of the first row are pinned at the base.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical load (masonry self-weight and floors load) is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement in the S-N direction, at the top and at the intermediate floor (at a height of 3 m), is gradually increased. S-N loading direction (positive) is considered. Constant ratios between the intermediate and top floor displacements are considered (1 at the top of the east wall, 0.88 at the top of the west wall and 0.6 at the intermediate floor level of both walls), so to represent a distribution of lateral forces approximately proportional to the fundamental mode shape.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.13, along with the walls damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the mean horizontal displacement at the top.

In addition, to evaluate the contribution of the transversal walls (North and South) on the overall longitudinal performances of the structure, the same analyses are performed also after disconnecting the walls at the intersections. The failure modes are evidenced in Fig. 4.14; the capacity curves are compared in Fig. 4.13 with the original configuration.

Fig. 4.12 Numerical model for analyses on pilot building.

The resistance contribution provided by the transversal walls is significant in this small and squat building. This is already evident in the study of the unreinforced configuration, where the transversal walls, due to the masonry tensile strength, delay the activation of the bending mechanism in the lateral piers of the longitudinal walls. The contribution of the transverse walls becomes even greater in the strengthened configuration, due the CRM tensile strength (applied also on the transversal walls and effectively connected at the foundation).

GB-B1

Fig. 4.13 Numerical analyses on the building: capacity curves and failure modes..

Fig. 4.14 Numerical analyses on the building with walls disconnected at the intersections: failure modes.

The same numerical model is used to simulate the performances of the experimental pilot building tested within the “CONSTRAIN” project. To adapt the model to the actual features of the experimental case, the following modifications are made:

- the masonry thickness is increased from 250 to 350 mm;
- the masonry mechanical characteristics are modified, accordingly to the different masonry type (rubble stone masonry Q2) - Table 4.2;
- the masonry jack arches are replaced by timber lintels indented in the masonry ~15 cm (elastic behavior, $E = 8000$ MPa). Just for the unstrengthened configuration, coherently with the findings of Report 1.2 [2], perfect bond between the lintel and the above masonry was considered (i.e. the mesh elements just above the lintel were assumed of masonry type).
- the presence of the horizontal ties is considered only the intermediate floor level (not at the top) and exclusively for the strengthened configurations;
- the ratios between the horizontal displacements applied to the longitudinal walls, at top and intermediate floors, are set accordingly with those recorded during the experiments.

Table 4.2 Main mechanical parameters adopted for the masonry of the CONSTRAIN pilot building (masonry type Q2)

	Q2 masonry	
Material type	<i>Cdpm2</i>	
Secant Young's modulus E	1.23 GPa	
Initial Young's modulus E_{init}	3.71 GPa	
Poisson modulus n	0.45	
Self-weight γ	21 kN/m ³	
Comp. strength f_c	2.0 MPa	
Tensile strength f_t	0.069 MPa	
Softening law	Linear	
Hardening parameters	b_h	0.027
	h_p	0.0
	k_{init}	0.075
Softening parameters	w_f/h	0.004
	a_{soft}	5.0

The results of the numerical simulations are summarized in Fig. 4.15, also in comparison with the experimental cyclic curves. Both S-N (positive, +) and N-S (negative, -) loading directions are analyzed.

Considering the simplifications of the numerical model, the numerical results are very well aligned with the experiments, both in terms of global capacity curves and damage modes of the elements (Fig. 4.16). Slightly lower resistance performance emerges in the numerical curves of the strengthened configuration, in the central part of the curves. This is likely due to the actual values of mortar coating tensile strength and thickness, that in the experimental test resulted slightly higher than the nominal ones used into the numerical simulations. However, numerical prediction of the reinforcement contribution in on the safe side.

GB-Q2-U

GB-Q2-R1

U+

R1+

Fig. 4.15 Numerical analyses on the "CONSTRAIN" pilot building: capacity curves and failure modes.

Fig. 4.16 Crack pattern of the strengthened configuration detected by DIC system at the end of the test (East wall).

5. Final remarks

In this report the results of the parametric analyses on benchmark examples are presented. The analyses were performed independently by the two partners (UL FGG and DIA-UNITS) in two different software environments: ABAQUS and OOFEM. The modelling approach and the material parameters are assumed the same as in the PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2].

The conclusions of the PRO-SIS Report 1.2 are that both modelling approaches give very similar results on specimens tested in CONSTRAIN project. However, as this report shows, there is a clear difference between the two modelling approaches in the parametric analyses, and consequently the results are much less aligned.

The key reason for the discrepancy is that ABAQUS and OOFEM models use different assumptions about the properties of the material in tension and compression. Both modelling approaches are purposefully based on homogenous model with tied connection between the masonry and the mortar coating. As such, the models cannot directly take into account the masonry anisotropy, as well as phenomena like brick (or stone) interlocking, coating delamination, friction and residual strength after cracking. In order to include these phenomena in the model, material constitutive laws were modified.

In the case of OOFEM, the tensile and compressive properties were modified. In particular, the post peak tensile law of masonry included a plateau before the failure, to account for friction and interlocking after cracking. Moreover, the tensile strength of the coating mortar was smoothed to better account for smear cracking. Additionally, the compressive strength of coating was drastically reduced to indirectly take into account the delamination of the plaster from the masonry support, which was observed experimentally and prevented exploitation of full compressive strength of mortar.

In the case of ABAQUS, the modifications were made only in the tensile part of the masonry material response: the post-peak behavior featured a partial strength drop followed by a constant residual capacity. Additionally, the ABAQUS models required the introduction of several contacts (local interactions) to obtain more realistic response matching the global behavior of the experiments.

The different approaches produced quite comparable results when simulating the individual benchmark elements, such as piers and spandrels, in terms on initial stiffness, peak resistance and damage mode. However, when the models were used on walls (or larger structural layouts in general), which include complex interaction between structural components, the difference in the global performance of the two models became relevant, although the damage pattern looked generally comparable.

Despite the difference between the modelling approaches, the analyses shown herein give a valuable insight into the response of the CRM strengthened masonry walls and buildings, and enable qualitative and quantitative comparisons. Importantly, they confirm the assumptions used in the design of CONSTRAIN strengthening, such as assumption of equivalent frame

approach, rigid sections between spandrels and piers, and the assumed response of each component.

Acknowledgments

The PRO-SIS project is funded by the Interreg VI-A Italy-Slovenia Programme 2021-2027, co-funded by the European Union.

All the project partners that actively contributed to the project are gratefully acknowledged.

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